

The Role of Social Humanities in Protecting Young People from Moral Threats in the Context of Globalization

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Abstract: In this article, it is described that at the stage of today's information society, it is very important to educate young people, to protect them from information attacks and spiritual threats, and to organize spiritual and educational promotion activities based on the requirements of the time. Therefore, in the education system, the main focus is on protecting our children from various ideological attacks and threats such as "mass culture", and on forming a conscious and active attitude to life and a sense of belonging in each of our young generations. people. Especially at the stage of today's information society, it is our responsibility to protect our children from threats such as various religious extremist, terrorist foreign ideas, and "mass culture".

Key words: "mass culture", the educational system, humanitarian sciences, national-spiritual heritage, philosophy, religious studies, civil society, the national idea, sociology, cultural studies, ethics and aesthetics.

There are many means and factors to protect our youth from moral threats and information attacks, among them, the continuous education system occupies the main role. It is in the educational system that young people's outlook and attitude to the world are formed, as well as their imagination and understanding of the scientific landscape of the world. in the educational system, these concepts and imaginations of our youth are formed primarily on the basis of social and humanitarian sciences. Therefore, it is the demand of the times to further improve the system of social and humanitarian sciences within the framework of the national idea aimed at educating the young generation in the spirit of national traditional values in continuous education, and to increase the effectiveness of research in this direction.

Children at all stages of the continuous education system, especially in the pre-school education system, are a national spiritual heritage, education on establishing the first concepts of national values and traditions, it is necessary to create a system of promotion and propaganda work and gradually accelerate. It is necessary to educate elementary school students in the spirit of valuing the national identity, respecting the unique traditions of our people, relying on the achievements of our national-spiritual heritage.

Educational stages in the continuous education system, it is appropriate to create educational state educational standards and develop curricula, expand social sciences related to the development of our national spiritual heritage. To prevent an ideological gap in the thinking of students and young people, to educate them in the spirit of nationalism and patriotism, in order to strengthen ideological immunity, the social and humanitarian sciences included in the curriculum of undergraduate education courses are the history of Uzbekistan, philosophy, religious studies, civil society, and the sciences of Uzbekistan's development strategy along with the national idea of Uzbekistan, the foundations of spirituality, the national idea, sociology, cultural studies, ethics and aesthetics, pathology, national-spiritual security, the foundations of sciences along with the national idea of Uzbekistan, the foundations of spirituality, the national idea, sociology, cultural studies, ethics and aesthetics, pathology, national-spiritual security, the foundations of sciences, In order to strengthen ideological immunity, the social and humanitarian sciences included in the curriculum of

undergraduate education courses are the history of Uzbekistan, philosophy, religious studies, civil society, and the sciences of Uzbekistan's development strategy along with the national idea of Uzbekistan, the foundations of spirituality, the national idea, sociology, cultural studies, ethics and aesthetics, pathology, national-spiritual security, the foundations of sciences, It is appropriate to introduce the subject "innovative ideological foundations of Uzbekistan's development" into the curriculum of master's majors, and the "ideological landscape of the world and national interests" course in all areas of basic doctoral studies.

In addition, it is necessary to organize an innovative approach to the study of the scientific and spiritual heritage of Central Asian thinkers in the system of social and humanitarian sciences. An innovative approach to the study of the scientific and spiritual heritage of Central Asian thinkers provides an opportunity to master our great national and spiritual heritage, and the national education system helps to achieve positive results.

In the process of modernization of education and training in the conditions of globalization, the system of social and humanitarian sciences should be made effective use of national-spiritual values and national spiritual heritage along with universal human values. In the current era of globalization, our national-spiritual heritage serves as an important tool in protecting our students from various spiritual threats and information attacks.

Protecting our students from religious fanaticism, extremist and terrorist operations is an important task of social and humanitarian sciences. From our national spiritual heritage, especially in the works of our thinkers, fanaticism, extremist and terrorist rocks are sharply condemned from the point of view of Islam, and their nefarious intentions are exposed in social and humanitarian sciences based on Islamic sources. This will help our students become immune to any religious fanaticism, extremist and terrorist ideas.

In the process of globalization, social and humanitarian sciences play an important role in the formation of the stability of ideological beliefs among young people. In the process of globalization, the stability of ideological beliefs of young people protects them from any ideological threats. The stability of ideological beliefs in young people allows them to develop a sense of patriotism. Reading culture plays an important role in the stability of ideological beliefs . Formation of reading culture among students in the information society is the main factor to protect them from moral threats and information attacks. Reading culture forms the basis of a person's intellectual potential. Young people with a culture of reading have their own independent outlook, historical memory, and a higher sense of national identity.

In the "higher education" stage of the continuous education system, the importance of social sciences is great in training highly qualified, competitive specialists, educating them to be spiritually mature, and forming a healthy ideological immunity in them. Today, social and humanitarian sciences are aimed at forming a sense of historical memory and national pride in young people, and a sense of pride in our national spiritual culture.

In the system of social and humanitarian sciences, it is necessary to strengthen the activities related to the research of the scientific heritage of our thinkers, and to strengthen the research on the translations of their works. Most of our great spiritual heritage remains untranslated. In order to encourage research related to the translation of these works, it is necessary to regularly organize various grant contests.

It is desirable to strengthen the philosophical methodological research of the translated works of our intellectual scholars. Philosophical and ethical works of our thinkers, which explain the principles of gratitude etiquette, serve as the theoretical basis of our national education system.

To sum up, the reduction of social and humanitarian sciences in the higher education system can cause spiritual poverty among students and complicate the responsible task of raising a mature generation. Filling the ideological gap that has appeared in the minds of young students is very complicated and takes a lot of time. It is necessary to understand the importance of social and humanitarian sciences in the education of a competent generation in the current complex

globalization era, where the struggle for human consciousness is going on. In addition, as we pay serious attention to the ideological and ideological education of young people at all stages of the continuous education system, it is appropriate to increase the number of subjects, topics and hours in the field of social and humanitarian sciences. Social and humanitarian sciences provide students with ideological and ideological literacy. Positive results are achieved in education of ideological and ideological immunity in students.